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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

A LEGEND FOR A ROMAN PREFECT: THE LAKES OF
PONTIUS PILATE¹

PART 1

1. The Sibyl is not alone

The Sibillini Mountain Range: a majestic, imposing natural feature raising in the Apennines, at the very center of Italy, between the provinces of

¹ Released on April 19th, 21st, 22nd, 24th, 26th, 29th and May 4th, 5th
(http://www.italianwriter.it/TheApennineSibyl/TheApennineSibyl_PilatusLakes.asp)

Umbria and Marche. A secluded region including a number of elevated peaks. A land of deep valleys, steep mountain-sides and small villages which have never been part of the main historical routes treaded through Italy by pilgrims, soldiers and wayfarers, the ancient roads that led to Rome and the harbours and towns of southern Italy. A place where the power of myth is still strong, and legendary tales have thrived for centuries, their sinister fame having spread throughout Europe for hundreds of years among travellers, men of letters and necromancers of all countries.

Fig. 1 - A vision of the Sibillini Mountain Range in the Apennines, central Italy (photo by Luigi Alesi)

In a previous series of articles (*Birth of a Sibyl: The Medieval Connection*) we have journeyed into the legend of the Apennine Sibyl, the mythical tale which, from the fifteenth century onwards, narrated of an enchanted realm concealed beneath the crowned peak of Mount Sibyl. On the mountain-top, a gloomy cavern provided an access to a subterranean land full of lavish palaces, precious treasures and sensual damsels, a hidden region ruled by a Queen Sibyl, an oracle and a prophetess, and an evil being looking for knights and their souls, to be held captive in an endless, unholy bliss until the end of the world.

Fig. 2 - Mount Sibyl in the Sibillini Mountain Range, as seen from its northern versant

In those articles, we carried out a hunt for the medieval roots of the Sibyl's fifteenth-century tales. We removed a collection of literary additions conferred to the legendary tale of the Apennine Sibyl, by taking off the concentric layers that encircled and suffocated the true mythical nucleus. We found out that an illustrious lineage for that Sibyl can be traced up to a medieval 'Sebile', a fay who is staged in many earlier chivalric poems and romances together with her more famed companion and alter ego: Morgan the Fay, a prominent character belonging to the Matter of Britain and the Arthurian cycle.

And we also found additional traces of something that goes even deeper: a few selected elements, a magical bridge, an ever-slamming metal gate, which are drawn from a much more antique tradition, pertaining to ancient narratives of travels into the Netherworld and the testing of the souls of mortal beings.

From this very point, from the paper *Birth of a Sibyl - The medieval connection*, we are now ready to start a new exciting travel and a veritable

plunge deep into the very core and meaning of the legend of the Apennine Sibyl.

However, before we tread this thrilling, wholly unknown road, we need to confront with another momentous task.

Because the legend of an Apennine Sibyl is not the one and only legend that lives within the same Sibillini Mountain Range, in Italy.

Another legend lives there. A different myth. A tale that is only 5.2 miles apart: the exact distance which lies between the cliff of Mount Sibyl and the spot where this further legend lies.

This is the legend of the Lakes of Pilate.

A legend that is set in the most secluded core of the Sibillini Mountain Range, as it is nested right within the rocky, titanic arms of Mount Vettore, the Range's most elevated peak.

Fig. 3 - The mysterious waters of the Lakes of Pilate, in the Sibillini Mountain Range

And this further legendary site looks straight into Mount Sibyl. Because the two sites, the Sibyl's cliff and the Lakes, are in full line of sight one another.

Let's start this new travel, too. And let's find out whether we can clean this second myth, too, of any narrative elements that have been added with time

to its story, possibly borrowed from other different mythical tales. Just as we did for the legend of the Apennine Sibyl. In search for an ultimate truth.

Fig. 4 - The peak of Mount Sibyl (standing out against the sky on the right side of the picture) as seen from the Lakes of Pilate

In our quest, we will take advantage of information provided in previous articles (*The Lake of Pilatus in an antique manuscript: Pierre Bersuire and the fourteenth-century dark renown of Norcia's lake*, and others). We will also draw on a remarkable paper published in 1893 by a great Italian scholar, Arturo Graf, providing a comprehensive summary on the ancient legends concerning Pontius Pilate and his resting place. And we will benefit from a number of scientific papers written on the same subject by illustrious specialists, including the recent works published by renowned researchers such as Anne-Catherine Baudoin and Jacques Berlioz.

Let's begin right now. And let's begin from the very place and setting in which the legend is harboured.

Let's begin from the lakes: the mysterious waters set in the deepest heart of the Sibillini Mountain Range, whose name is, even today, the Lakes of Pilate.

2. The awe-inspiring hollow of Mount Vettore

At the very centre of Italy the fastnesses of the Sibillini Mountain Range, a portion of the Italian Apennines, stand out from the main chain as an impregnable fortress. On the southernmost side of this massive ridge, facing the crowned peak of Mount Sibyl, raises the titanic shape of Mount Vettore, with its huge, imposing mass, an arched behemoth that overwhelms the whole mountainous region with its elevated top and vertiginous, sinister cliffs.

Fig. 5 - Mount Vettore in the Italian Sibillini Mountain Range, with its astounding U-shaped landform

Deeply enclosed within the precipitous arms of this giant of stone, two small mirrors of pure, clear water lie in silence and stillness. They are the Lakes of Pilate, waiting in their solitary nest, surrounded by looming, overhanging versants of vertical rock.

Fig. 6 - The cliffs of Mount Vettore with the Lakes of Pilate nested within the glacial cirque

The Lakes of Pilate: two icy, crystal-like surfaces, set at the bottom of Mount Vettore's glacial cirque, high up amid sheer walls of rock, quietly reflecting the sky above.

Fig. 7 - The Lakes of Pilate sitting beneath vertical walls of rock

Whoever had the chance to climb the gigantic mountain and visit the place hidden between the cliffs of rock knows well the feeling of indistinct, dumbfounded awe that seizes a human soul when left alone before this

overpowering might, echoing any step that may be taken, any sound and any word that might be uttered, with hesitant whispers, by the unwary visitor.

This is a truly blood-curdling place. A sort of theatrical scenery, ready for some kind of eerie performance. It is a setting where an inexplicable, dreadful event seems to be about to happen.

Fig. 8 - The mysterious setting of the Lakes of Pilate

The above description has much of the poetical and the literary. However, it is the very nature of the site that conveys the listed feelings, bringing to the mind a weird impression of apprehension and expectation.

Mount Vettore is the result of the titanic strain produced by the clash of two tectonic plates, confronting each other over the full length of the Apennines and colliding with giant might in the area of today's Sibillini Mountain Range. Ten million years ago the mountainous landform began to raise its peaks and crests from the bottom of a vanished sea. The process lasted many million years and the geological outcome was the massive ridges we see today.

It was at the end of the Pleistocene, during the Würm glaciation, a period extending from 100,000 to 10,000 years ago, that the Ice Age produced the

most impressive feature which marks Mount Vettore as we know it today: the glacial cirque, a colossal hemicycle carved in the very matrix of the landform, which gives the mount its fantastic, astounding U-shaped structure, a sort of immense horseshoe. A glacier made all this, eroding and grinding the mount's rock by its ceaseless motion under the pull of gravity, for hundreds and hundreds of centuries.

Fig. 9 - Mount Vettore, the most imposing elevation of the Sibillini Mountain Range

Today, the ancient glacier has vanished, but the savage effects of its incessant action are fully visible. Mount Vettore is hollowed out from the inside: a large valley is carved in its bowels, going from the elevated cliffs above, the razor-sharp rim of a rocky semicircular wall, straight down to the lower lands below, surrounded by further peaks, including Mount Sibyl.

Up there, at the very centre of a vertiginous hemisphere of stone, whose walls are more than 1,500 feet high, the Lakes of Pilate stand, feeding on rainfall and molten snow, away from human life, totally enshrouded in silence.

Fig. 10 - The glacial cirque of Mount Vettore (on the top portion of the picture) and the hollow carved by the displacement of the ancient glacier

They are not entirely alone, because their waters are inhabited by a small living being: a tiny shrimp, around 0.4 inches long, featuring an elegant coral-red colouring, a delicate animal which swims and drifts within the boundaries of the two icy lakes. The *Chirocephalus Marchesonii* can only be found there, fully adapted to the harsh environmental conditions, with its minute determination to survive.

Fig. 11 - The *Chirocephalus Marchesonii*, the small shrimp which lives in the Lakes of Pilate

Such are the Lakes of Pilate, set in the middle of the Sibillini Mountain Range. And if you look down, along the valley which follows the antique glacier's displacement route, you will enjoy a gorgeous vista. A vista which is dominated by the crowned peak of Mount Sibyl. Five miles away, and in full view.

The Lakes of Pilate: this is a place where an obscure, sinister legend might certainly resolve to settle down.

As it actually did. And all this occurred under the name of Pontius Pilate, the prefect of Judaea.

3. A legendary plunge into cold waters

In our previous article we described the nature of the Lakes of Pilate, sitting at the very centre of a glacial cirque in the Sibillini Mountain Range, and the weird aura that lingers on that site. Certainly it appears to be as a place particularly fit to host an eerie legend. And this is actually the case.

But what sort of legendary tale did settle here?

Let's begin with the words written on the subject by a recognised expert: Antoine de la Sale, the French gentleman who visited Mount Sibyl on May, 18th 1420 and put down an account of his venturesome excursion in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, a work contained in a most precious illuminated manuscript, no. 0653 (0924) preserved at the Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé) in Chantilly (France).

The manuscript, enriched with a bounty of fine miniatures, portrays what Antoine de la Sale calls, at folium 2v, the «mountain of the lake of Queen Sibyl, which some name the mountain of the lake of Pilate [...] part of the Duchy of Spoletium and in the territory of the town of Norcia» (in the original French text: «mont du lac de la royne sibille, que aulcuns appellent le mont du lac de pillate [...] parties de la Duchié despollit et au terroir de la cite de Norse»).

Fig. 12 - The opening of Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* with the mention of a Lake of Pilate (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 2v)

At the very beginning of our search, we stumble right upon a remarkable piece of information: the lake is referred to by Antoine de la Sale as a feature which is in strong, direct connection to the Sibyl and her mount, so much so that the lake is first named after the Sibyl, and only secondarily it is indicated as linked to Pilate.

And this sound connection is effectively depicted by Antoine de la Sale in a remarkable miniature (folia 5v - 6r) which shows the two mountains, facing one another, the way they stand in actual reality: Mount Vettore, sitting on the left side of the picture with his lake set beneath the mountain-top; and Mount Sibyl, on the right side, with its mysterious cave carved on the cliff, which is surmounted by its most renowned crown of precipitous rock. A

powerful graphical representation of a clue that we will fully address later in this and subsequent articles.

Fig. 13 - The drawing which shows Mount Sibyl and today's Mount Vettore in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folia 5v - 6r)

But let's stick to Antoine de la Sale's description, and see how he reports the odd legend that lived on that eerie mountain:

«Tales are told that when Titus son of Vespasian, the Emperor of Rome, had crushed down the town of Jerusalem, which some say that it was made to avenge the death of Our Lord Jesus Christ [...] when he came back to Rome he brought with him Pilate who at that time was an officier at the said town of Jerusalem».

[In the original French text: «se compte que quant titus de vespasien empeur de romme eut destruite la cite de Jherusalem la quelle aucuns disent que ce fut pour la vengeance de la mort Nostre Sieu Jhesuscrist [...] au

retour que fist a romme, mena avecques soy pillate qui pour ce temps estoit officier en la ditte cite de Jherusalem»].

Fig. 14 - The excerpt on Titus and Pilate from Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 2v)

So we see that the legendary tale, according to «the way local people report it» («la forme du parler des gens d'iceluy pays» in French), is marked by a significant trait, as it is situated in a most definite Christian context: revenge for the Passion, punishment for a town where Jesus Christ was betrayed and put to death. And a special treatment is envisaged for a personage who was individually responsible for the killing of the Son of God (folium 2v):

«[...] following the will of the people of Rome, he [the Emperor] decided to put him to death on the ground that Pilate had not intended to condemn our true saviour Jesus Christ, yet he had failed in his duty to preserve him from death».

[In the original French text: «[...] voyant tout le peuple il le fist mourir suppose que pillate ne voullist oncques condampner nostredit vray sauveur Jhesuscrist mais pour ce quil ne fist son devoir a le garantir de mort»].

Fig. 15 - The passage on Pilate's guilt from Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 2v)

Thus, the legend has its main character: a villain, a man who, as we know from the Gospels, had certainly a major part in the murder of Jesus, owing to the post he was holding at that time as a prominent Roman authority in the occupied Judaea.

But what has it all got to do with the Sibillini Mountain Range in Italy? Here is how Antoine de la Sale reports what he was told by local people (folium 4r):

Fig. 16 - The excerpt on Pilate's last wish from Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 4r)

«Furthermore people say that when Pilate saw that there was no way left for him to save his own life, he asked to be granted a last wish, which was accorded to him: he demanded that after his death his body be placed on a

chariot drawn by two pairs of buffaloes and allowed to wander wherever the buffaloes may lead it. And they tell this is what was actually done».

[In the original French text: «Encores disent les gens que quant pilate vit que de sa vie ny avoit nul remede plus, il supplia un don qui lui fut accorde alors requist que apres sa mort son corps feust mis sur un char attelle de deux paires de buffles et feust laissie aler la ou laventure des buffles le porteroit et ainsi dient que fut fait»].

And here is the core of the legend, the connection to Mount Sibyl and the neighbouring mountain, known today as Mount Vettore:

«But the Emperor, who wondered at this request, wished to be informed of the course taken by the chariot, so he ordered his men to follow it until the buffaloes reached the shore of this lake and threw themselves into the waters together with all the chariot and Pilate's corpse, and they did it so quickly as if they were being chased with the utmost haste. And this is the reason for which this lake is called after Pilate».

[In the original French text: «Mais l'empereur qui se esmerveilla de ceste requeste si vult scavoir ou le chair adresseroit si le fist suivre tant que les buffles vindrent au bout de ce lac si se bouterent a tout le char et le corps de pilate dedens ainsi hastivement que se on les suivist batant le plus que len pourroit. Et pour ceste raison est dit le lac de pilate»].

Fig. 17 - The core of Pilate's legendary tale from Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 4r)

A lake dedicated to Pontius Pilate, an ancient Roman prefect who ruled Judaea when Jesus underwent his atrocious Passion. Right in the middle of the Sibillini Mountain Range, in Italy.

Yet Antoine de la Sale does not miss the chance to emphasize again the fact that these waters are also known as a Sibyl's Lake (folia 4r - 4v):

«Others call it the lake of the Sibyl because Mount Sibyl is right before it and connected to the lake, apart from a small streamlet which runs between them in the way portrayed in the following figure» («Les autres l'appellent le lac de la sibille pour ce que le mont de la sibille est devant et joignant a cestu fors dun petit ruisseau qui court entre deux en la maniere que cy apres est pourtrait»).

Fig. 18 - The name of the Sibyl is associated with the Lake of Pilate in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folia 4r - 4v)

How can it be that a legend on Pontius Pilate, who has nothing to do with the Sibillini Mountain Range, got stuck exactly here? And why did the myth choose a place which is already linked, someway and somehow, to a different legend, that of an Apennine Sibyl?

Before we try to answer all such critical questions, we still have to peruse the words written by Antoine de la Sale in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*.

We will stumble upon additional clues that might put our investigation on the right track. Let's go and find out.

4. A chariot, an islet, many necromancers and lots of guards

A lake lies on elevated grounds in the middle of Mount Vettore's glacial cirque, within the Italian Sibillini Mountain Range. And, according to a legend narrated by Antoine de la Sale, a fifteenth century French author, the lake is named after Pontius Pilate.

Manuscript no. 0653 (0924), preserved at the Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé) in Chantilly (France), contains Antoine de la Sale's "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl", in which the French gentleman tells his readers an odd story about a chariot, two pairs of buffaloes and the dead corpse of Pilate, all of them eventually cast into the lake's icy waters following an amazing race up the mountain-side.

And an astounding miniature, at folium 4r of the manuscript, portrays Pontius Pilate himself lying on his chariot pulled by the four buffaloes: a vivid representation of such an utterly bizarre tale.

Fig. 19 - The chariot with the body of Pontius Pilate in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 4r)

From the lake, Mount Sibyl with its enchanted cave, the abode of an Apennine Sibyl, is in full view.

What does it all mean? Why do so many legends, at all appearances featuring utterly different traits, seem to insist on the same location, in central Italy?

Let's make an attempt at finding further clues in the said manuscript. As we already detailed, the parchment leaves contain the account that de la Sale wrote two decades after he paid a visit to Mount Sibyl on May, 18th 1420. In the manuscript, the French man of letters provides a detailed description of what was to be found at the lake:

«This lake, in my opinion, is the size of your town of Moulins» («Ce lac est en mon semblant du tour de vostre ville de moulins»).

Fig. 20 - The comparison between the lake and the town of Moulins in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 4v)

We must recall that Antoine de la Sale wrote his account for the enjoyment of Agnes of Burgundy, Duchess of Bourbon. The town of Moulins-sur-Allier was the capital of the Duchy of Bourbon, in central France. As an interesting exercise, we can easily calculate the size of the ancient castle of Moulins by comparing a map drawn by the Cassini family in the eighteenth century with the corresponding satellite view taken from GoogleMaps: the downtown area of modern Moulins, corresponding to the original castle, is around 1,300 feet wide (as marked by the yellow ruler in the figure). This is not so different from the size of the valley housing the two lakes of Pilate which we see today, marked by the same ruler for the sake of comparison. Thus the estimate provided by Antoine de la Sale is fairly right.

Fig. 21 - The French town of Moulins-sur-Allier in an eighteenth-century map and in a modern satellite view

Fig. 22 - The glacial cirque of Mount Vettore with the Lakes of Pilate and a comparison ruler which shows the size of the historical district of Moulins-sur-Allier

In our present times, we actually have two small lakes, instead of only one as it appears in Antoine de la Sale's fifteenth-century description. However, we must be aware that in the subsequent five centuries many landslides, often caused by violent earthquakes, have fallen onto the lake from the looming 'Pizzo del Diavolo', the sheer wall of rock which surmounts the waters: as a result, the bottom of the glacial cirque in which the lakes rest has gradually increased in elevation, as the debris filled up the hollow, until the lake split in two the way they appear today. Anyway, in years when snow and rain are abundant, the two lakes still tend to merge into one, as it can be noticed in recent pictures.

Fig. 23 - The Lakes of Pilate as they appear when water is abundant

So Antoine de la Sale's description can be considered as very accurate. Yet de la Sale is even more rigorous than that. He also depicts what was to be encountered at the very center of the lake, a feature that today has completely disappeared under the rubble cast on it by hundreds of years of landslides:

«In the middle there is a small islet made of one boulder which was once walled all around, and the lower portion of this wall is still extant in many points. From the shore to the small island there is a narrow walkway submerged by the water which is five feet high as people told me; that passage was broken down by the local residents so as to make it impracticable, so that those who reached the island to consecrate their books by the art of necromancy wouldn't be able to find it anymore».

[In the original French text: «Au milieu a une petite islete dun rochier qui jadis fut muree tout en tour encores y sont les fondemens du mur en plusieurs lieux. De la terre à celle isle a une petite chausse couverte deau a la haulteur de v piez comme les gens me dirent laquelle fust rompue tant quon ne la peust cuier par les gens du pais affin que ceulz qui aloient en lisle consacrer leurs livres pour lart dingromance ne la peussent trouver»].

Fig. 24 - The passage on the Lake Pilate's islet in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 4v)

As you can see, the legend is getting increasingly entangled. Now we are considering not only a resting place for Pontius Pilate, but also a place suitable for practicing forbidden black arts.

But the story is even more perplexing than that. A third element is introduced by the author, which seems to have nothing to do with all the rest:

«That island is strictly guarded and protected from the local people on the ground that when anybody comes to it covertly and performs the art of the Fiend, after the operation is made a storm so violent raises in the region that all crops and goods in the country get spoiled».

[In the original French text: «La quelle isle est moult gardee et deffendue des gens du pais pource que quant aucun y vient selement et a fait son art de l'ennemy apres se fait se lieve une tempeste si grant par le pais qui gaste tous les fruiz et biens de la contree»].

Fig. 25 - The remarkable passage on the tempests which are raised by art of necromancy at the Lake of Pilate in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 4v)

What is the meaning of all that? Is it just a foolish tale, a silly rumour circulating amid the populace and the local villagers? Not in the least. Because people seemed to truly believe in that, and foreigners did actually come to the lake to the said evil purposes, so much so that drastic countermeasures were often taken:

«For this reason when the local people, who take great care in that, find someone there, he his not welcome. And not much time has elapsed since two men were caught, one of them being a priest. The priest was brought to the said town of Norcia and there was martyred and burnt. The other was

slaughtered into pieces and then thrown into the lake from the very people who had caught them both».

[In the original French text: «Et porce quant les gens du pays qui ad ce prennent moult grant garde y trouvent aucun il est mal venu. Et navoit pas long temps quel y fut prins deux hommes dont lun estoit prestre ce preste fut admene a la dicte cite de norce et la fut martire et ars. Lautre fut taille a pieces et puis boute dedens le lac par ceulz qui les avoient prins»].

Fig. 26 - The killing of supposed necromancers at the Lake of Pilate in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folia 4v - 5r)

However, continues Antoine de la Sale, honourable visitors are always allowed to pay a visit to the lake, if they obtain a clearance from the local authorities:

«But if anybody wishes to see the said lake, for his own safety it is advisable to ask the rulers of the above town, who will gladly provide a permit to see it with no other requirements, provided that they go as upright men would do».

[In the original French text: «Mais si aucun prenoit plaisir a veoir ce dit lac pour lasseurete de sa personne lui convient aler aux seigneurs de la dicte

cite qui volentiers lui donneront conduit pour ce veoir sans aultre chose faire, sil vait en estat domme de bien»].

Fig. 27 - Well-intentioned visitors at the Lake of Pilate in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 5r)

This is how Antoine de la Sale, in his fifteenth-century account, depicts the Lake of Pilate and the gloomy tales which loomed over the glacial cirque of Mount Vettore, in Italy.

Why should the body of Pontius Pilate have been buried as far as such remote waters hidden in the very core of the Italian Sibillini Mountain Range? What do necromancers have to do with a lake hosting a dead Roman prefect in it? And why black arts should be performed in so outlandish a place?

We will try to provide an answer to all the listed questions. And we will start our enquiry from the puzzled statements written on the subject, in his “The Paradise of Queen Sibyl”, by Antoine de la Sale himself.

5. The distrust by Antoine de la Sale

In 1420, Antoine de la Sale pushed himself as far as the Sibillini Mountain Range in central Italy; there, he found not only a mount and a cave considered as the abode of a Sibyl, but also a lake, located a few miles from the Sibyl's mount, into which, according to a legendary tale, the body of Pontius Pilate, sentenced to death by Emperor Titus, would have been

thrown together with the chariot that was transporting it. In addition to that, the lake had become a site of choice for necromancers to perform their forbidden arts, producing violent storms in the region.

Fig. 28 - The mount of the Lake of Pilate and Mount Sibyl in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folia 5v - 6r)

Antoine de la Sale, who was a young but experienced courtier, was fully aware of the inconsistencies that marked this odd legend about Pilate:

«Which I think it is untrue because they maintain that Titus sentenced Pilate to death, but Titus came much time after Pilate, who lived at the time and under the rule of Emperor Tiberius, and he was his official in the said town of Jherusalem».

[In the original French text: «Laquelle chose jetrouve faulse en tant quilz dient que titus eust fait mourir pilate car titus fut grant espace apres pillate qui estoit du temps et soubz l'empire de l'empereur thibere et son officier en la dicte cité de Jherusalem»].

Fig. 29 - The unconvinced statement written by Antoine de la Sale in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 4v)

As a matter of fact, it is highly improbable that Emperor Titus, who reigned from 79 to 81 A.D., might have had anything to do with a prefect who was in charge more than forty years earlier, when the same Emperor was not yet born. So, certainly there is something wrong with the legend's details.

De la Sale properly notes that if any Emperor had ever murdered Pontius Pilate, that Emperor should have been Tiberius, who ruled from 14 to 37 A.D., during the years when Jesus Christ was crucified in Jerusalem. In an attempt to clarify the issue, the French author quotes an extensive excerpt drawn from Paulus Orosius, an early-Christian theologian and historian who lived between the fourth century and the fifth:

«As Orosius reports in the second chapter of his eighth book, in which he says that after the death and resurrection of Jesus Christ Pilate sent to the said Tiberius the grand and amazing news about the trial, death and resurrection of the said Jesus of Nazareth [...] by which many people was already convinced that he truly was God or son of God. And that report and letters Tiberius right away forwarded to the Senate [...] eagerly asking the senators to honour that Jesus of Nazareth and consider him as a true god. But the Senate, who greatly opposed Pilate on the ground that he had not first written to them, rejected the Emperor's request and issued an order out of spite, which was immediately sent to Jerusalem that all the followers and disciples of that Jesus of Nazareth be taken and prosecuted. And, on his side, hearing of all that, the Emperor, out of spite too, sent orders that they be helped and favoured and supported instead by all means. So here began a conflict between the senators and the Emperor».

[In the original French text: «Sicomme dit Orose ou second chappitre de son viii livre qui disioit que apres la mort et la resurrection de Jhesucrist pilate envoya au dit thibere cesar les treshaultes et merueilleuses nouvelles et le proces de la mort et resurrection du nomme Jhesus de Nazaret [...] par lesquelles ja maintes gens croioient que il feust Dieu ou filz de dieu vrayement. Le quel proces et lettres le dit empereur incontinant manda aux senateurs [...] priant moult estroittement le senat que icelui jhesus de nazareth feust consacré et tenu a vray dieu. Mais le senat qui fut grandement contre pillate car navoit premierement rescript a eulx reffusa la consecration et fist un esdit par despit que incontinent manderent en Jherusalem prendre et persecuter tous les disciples et croians en icellui jhesus de nazareth. Et dautre part sentant l'empereur ceste chose

semblablement par despit deulx remanda que ilz feussent aidiez favorizez et soustenuz a tout pouvoir. Lors commença le debat des senateurs a l'empereur»].

Fig. 30 - The excerpt taken from Paulus Orosius as quoted by Antoine de la Sale in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folia 2v - 3r)

In this specific excerpt taken from Orosius, the ancient Latin author says nothing about Pilate's death. However, Antoine de la Sale provides the reader with his own assumption:

«In this way the majority of those who had opposed the consecration of Jesus Christ were killed. In this predicament, it might well be that he [Tiberius] had Pilate murdered, but certainly not Titus, the son of Vespasian, in spite of what local people may say. So we can see here that this is a first mistake of them».

[In the original French text: «aussi moururent presque tous qui avoient este contraires a la consecration de Jhesucrist. Par la quelle chose peut bien

estre quil fist mourir pilate, mais non pas titus de vespasien ainsi que ceulx dudit pais dient. Et voies icy leur premiere erreur»].

Fig. 31 - Antoine de la Sale's remarks on the death of Pilate in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 3r)

That was all that Antoine de la Sale could tell his readers about the weird, amazing, bizarre legend of the Lake of Pilate, nested within precipitous mountains in the middle of the Italian peninsula.

Many things he said; yet not clear enough to have a clue on what all that meant, and still means.

And the issues do not end here.

In fact, there is one critical, specific issue concerning the legend of the Lakes of Pilate. Actually, more than one issue.

Because the Lakes of Pilate are not alone. It actually seems that Pontius Pilate, the ancient prefect of Roman-occupied Judaea, the man who washed his hands while sentencing Jesus Christ to death, underwent a peculiar fate.

He was buried more than once. In different places.

There are several resting places for the mortal remains of Pilate. Scattered across various lakes and mounts around Europe. And, for each one of them, there is a legend.

Fig. 32 - Pontius Pilate washing his hands

And such legends are very, very similar to that one narrated by Antoine de la Sale with relation to the Sibillini Mountain Range.

What does it all mean? Which places and legends are we talking about? What is the link, if any, which connects them all?

To answer all these questions, let's start our journey into the many tales which narrate of Pontius Pilate and his burial site. And let's see what happens.

6. The many resting places of the governor of Judaea

In our previous articles, we have perused the pages of *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, a fifteenth-century work by Antoine de la Sale which presents the legendary tale of the death of Pontius Pilate, the Roman prefect of Judaea, and his burial into a small lake set amid the Sibillini Mountain Range, in which his body was thrown. A lake that became a place of black magic and necromancy, and whose name is connected still today to that of Pilate.

Fig. 33 - The Lakes of Pilate, mysterious mirrors reflecting the sky above

Why did a legend concerning the renowned Roman prefect who sentenced Jesus Christ to death settle in this very corner of central Italy, having at all appearances nothing to do with any of the events narrated in the Gospels?

To find it out, let's continue our reading of ancient clues contained in further manuscripts. Here is a second story which might be of interest to us:

«And about Pontius Pilate it is written, in the 'Beheading of St. John the Baptist', that after having been accused by the Jews to be the infamy of his kindred, he was exiled to Lyon in order to be sentenced; there, he was sentenced to starvation. And in that same place where he was born it is said that he killed himself out of grief. Others say that in Lyon he was condemned to be hanged, and he was actually hanged in Vienne; still in the church of the Holy Mary, an iron hook is shown to which people say he was suspended».

[In the original Latin text: «Et de Pontyo Pilato dicitur, in decollatione sancti Johannis Baptiste, quod accusatus a Judeis in obproprium sui generis

mittitur apud Lugdunum in exilium dampnandus, ubi, ut dicitur, dampnatus est sic ut nihil comederet. Qui ibidem ubi oriundus fuerat, ut dicitur, pre dolore se occidit. Alii dicunt quod Lugduni suspendio adjudicatus et apud Viennam est suspensus et ostenditur adhuc ibi, in ecclesia beate Marie, uncus ferreus in quo dicitur fuisse suspensus»].

Fig. 34 - The opening folium and the excerpt on Pilate as it appears in Stephen of Bourbon's *Tractatus de diversis materiis predicabilibus* (manuscript Latin 15970, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 180r)

This is a further tale on the death of Pontius Pilate which is found in Stephen of Bourbon's *Tractatus de diversis materiis predicabilibus*, written in the first half of the thirteenth century. In Part I *De timore* (*On fear*), Section VII *De timore mortis* (*On the fear of death*), as it appears in manuscript Latin 15970 preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France at folium 180r, the preacher of the Dominican order narrates of a verdict

issued against Pilate, of his possible suicide or, as an alternative tale, of his hanging from a hook in Vienne, a French town set fifteen miles south of Lyon, by the great river Rhône. As we will later see, Stephen of Bourbon is making reference to another work, the *Abbreviatio in gestis et miraculis sanctorum*, in which Jean de Mailly, another Dominican preacher, mentions Pilate's exile while illustrating the story of St. John the Baptist.

However, Stephen of Bourbon has something more to say. A piece of information it seems we have already heard of:

«And not far from that same place, on a mount near St. Chamon, he [Pilate] was hurled into a pit; from this pit, when a stone is thrown into it, people say vapours are issued, and storms arise».

[In the original Latin text: «et ibi prope in monte supra Saint Chamon in puteo projectus; ubi, quando lapis proicitur, fumus inde egredi dicitur, de quo tempestas concitatur»].

Fig. 35 - The subsequent sentence of the excerpt on Pilate from Stephen of Bourbon's *Tractatus de diversis materiis predicabilibus* (manuscript Latin 15970, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 180r)

Pontius Pilate, the prefect of the Roman province of Judaea, was thrown into a pit, or well, lying on a mount. Just like in Antoine de la Sale's account. And - as in that account - storms seem to raise from that odd resting place, into which Pilate's body was hurled.

Are we in the middle of the Sibillini Mountain Range, in Italy?

Not at all. Instead, we are in France, nor far from Lyon, on a mount raising its peak in the vicinity of Saint-Chamond, an ancient town which is set at the foot of a mountainous relief.

And the relief, still today, is called the 'Massif de Pilat': the mountain range of Pilate, whose peaks are collectively said 'Mont de Pilat'.

Fig. 36 - Sunset on the peaks called 'Les Trois Dentes' set in the Massif de Pilat, central France

So we find ourselves with two different legendary resting plates for our most renowned prefect: the first is in Italy, and the second in France.

Isn't that enough? No, because we also have a third. In Switzerland. And the relevant description is not dissimilar from the previous two:

«Pilatus [...] wrote to Tiberius that [...] Jesus] had been crucified, and described to the Emperor all the miracles that He had done. Having been informed that He had really been crucified, he regretted His death [...] So

he summoned Pilate to Rome. When the prefect reached Rome and reported to Tiberius on Jesus Christ's death, the Emperor put him in prison, and devised to contrive a harrowing death to have him killed. But when Pilatus knew that he was going to die because of Jesus' death, he killed himself in the prison. He was found dead and his body was thrown into the river Tiber, but the demons put the town at risk with his corpse. For this reason Tiberius had his body taken off the river and brought near Amona [Vienne], where he was thrown into the river Rhône. But there, too, the demons raised many storms and hail around his corpse».

Fig. 37 - The passage on Pontius Pilate which appears in selected manuscripts of Godfrey of Viterbo's *Speculum regum* (from *Monumenta Germaniae Historica*, Tomus XXII Scriptorum, Hannover 1872, p. 70-71, transcription by George Waitz)

[In the original Latin text: «Pilate [...] rescripsit Tiberio [...] Ihesum] esse crucifixum, et cetera aliqua de miraculis que per eum facta sunt. Audiens vero Tiberius [...] illum crucifixisse, doluit de morte eius [...] Direxerat enim ad Pilatum, ut ad se veniret Romam. Qui dum Romam venisset et de morte Christi per eum Tiberius informatus esset, Pilatum incarceravit, volens excogitare mortem turpissimam, qua eum occideret. Intelligens vero Pilatus propter mortem Ihesu se moriturum, se in carcere interfecit, et mortuus repertus in Tiberim proiectus, et demones cum corpore suo multa pericula intulerunt in patria. Quare a Tiberi levatus et iuxta Amonam

[Viennam] in Rodanum ductus est et projectus; ubi similiter demones multas tempestates et grandines iuxta corpus suum fecerunt»].

This description, which will experience a great diffusion, as we will later see, is included in a thirteenth-century anonymous commentary to the *Speculum regum*, written a century earlier by Godfrey of Viterbo, a secretary to Emperor Frederick I Barbarossa. The excerpt is contained in selected manuscripts bearing the *Speculum*, as reported by G. Waitz in a transcript published in 1872, from which we quote.

You may note that Pilatus' resting place, as it is mentioned in the excerpt above, is that same Vienne we already found in Stephen of Bourbon. And storms are always present, ready to rage the river's waters. However, the ancient comment proceeds further on:

«The people took Pilate's body off the Rhône and, after having reached the mountains not far from Lausanne, in the proximity of Lucerne, hurled him into a marsh. And sure enough, when anybody throws an object, small as it may be, into the marsh [pit], at once storms and hail and lightnings and thunders hit the land. Therefore there are men who guard the place, especially in summers, lest any foreigners climb the mount».

corpus suum fecerunt²⁰. Ideo patrioti^b experti de corpore Pilati, de Rodano receperunt et *** in montanis circa Losoniam^c prope Lucernam²¹ in quendam paludem^d proiecerunt^e. Et certum est, quod quandocumque aliquis homo^f aliquid^g quantumcumque parvum mittit in paludem^h, tunc in continenti fiunt tempestates, grandines, fulgura et tonitrua. Ideo sunt homines custodes constituti, qui tempore estatis custodiunt, ne aliquis advena ascendat. —

c) Losoniam 2^a; Lofoniam 2^b.

h) fo- veam 3^b;

Fig. 38 - The subsequent sentence of the passage on Pontius Pilate which appears in selected manuscripts of Godfrey of Viterbo's *Speculum regum* (from *Monumenta Germaniae Historica*, Tomus XXII Scriptorum, Hannover 1872, p. 71, transcription by George Waitz)

[In the original Latin text: «Ideo patrioti experti de corpore Pilati, de Rodano receperunt et in montanis circa Losoniam prope Lucernam in quendam paludem proiecerunt. Et certum est, quod quandocumque aliquis homo aliquid quantumcumque parvum mittit in paludem [foveam], tunc in continenti fiunt tempestates, grandines, fulgura et tonitrua. Ideo sunt

homines custodes constituti, qui tempore estatis custodiunt, ne aliquis advena ascendat»].

And here is a third resting place for Pontius Pilate: we have now reached Switzerland, and we have landed in Lucerne, together with the prefect's body. According to this version of the legend, the corpse was hurled into a marsh, or, in some manuscripts, a pit. Storms are never missing, now they rather seem to be even fiercer.

And you know what? There is a mountain which just overlooks the Swiss town of Lucerne. Its name is Tomlishorn. It is also commonly known, even in our present days, as 'Mont Pilate'.

Fig. 39 - The peak of the Tomlishorn, or Mont Pilate, Lucerne, central Switzerland

So let's try to summarise our legendary collection. We are dealing with three legends concerning the same Pontius Pilatus, the man who ordered Jesus Christ to be crucified. And we have in our hands three different burial places for our poor Roman prefect.

The first one is a lake set in the Sibillini Mountain Range in Italy, as reported by Antoine de la Sale in the fifteenth century. In the lake, demons

reside who can raise storms. The place is called, still today, the Lakes of Pilatus.

The second site is some sort of pit set near Lyon in France, as reported by Stephen of Bourbon in the thirteenth century. In the pit, some thing resides, and storms arise from it. The place is situated on a mountain which is called, still today, Mont de Pilat.

The third location is another pit lying near Lucerne in Switzerland, as reported by unknown thirteenth-century hands on manuscripts bearing a work by Godfrey of Viterbo. The pit contains some unknown thing, so that storms can raise from it. It is not a mere chance that the mount set by Lucerne is called, still today, Mont Pilate.

Fig. 40 - Three different sites in Italy, France and Switzerland which harbour a legend on Pontius Pilate's burial place

We might as well go on with further places in which Pontius Pilate would allegedly have been buried. In his *Fabularius*, Conradus de Mure, a thirteenth-century Swiss scholar, writes that the corpse of Pilate, after its usual troubled plunge «in Rodanum apud Viennam», was brought «in alpes apud montem septimum», possibly a reference to the Swiss Alps and the Septimer Pass, which connects the northern region around the Lake of Como, Italy, to Switzerland.

Fig. 41 - The passage on Pontius Pilate from Conradus de Mure's *Fabularius* (manuscript Latin 8169A, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folia 98r - 98v)

The mystery gets darker and darker, as the figure of Pontius Pilate seems to sneer at our bewilderment from the many resting places in which he lies, raising tempests from them and hiding himself beneath the icy waters of the Lakes of Pilatus in Italy.

So what to do next?

For a better understanding of the whole matter concerning Pilate, his gloomy burial sites, and the sinister legend which lives amid the Sibillini Mountain Range, the time has come to deepen our knowledge of the main character of this strange legend.

Who was Pontius Pilate?

Or, better still, who was he according to ancient literary sources? Is there any extant description of the circumstances of his death? And why would he be linked with any specific, peculiar resting place? And, finally, what is

the reason for the connection between the Roman prefect and the lakes nested within the Sibillini Mountain Range?

In the next article, we are going to meet the fifth prefect of Roman-occupied Judaea. We are going to meet Pontius Pilate.

And it will be a close encounter.

7. An uncompromising portrait of the governor of Judaea

In 1961, an Italian archeologist, Antonio Frova, who was carrying out an excavation campaign at the ancient site of Caesarea Maritima, Israel, unearthed a stone bearing an utmostly rare fragmentary inscription:

Fig. 42 - The Pilate Stone, now preserved at the Israel Museum in Jerusalem

«To the Divine Augusti Tiberieum - Pontius Pilate - Prefect of Judaea - Made and dedicated this».

[In the original Latin text: «[Dis Augusti]S Tiberieum - [Po]ntius Pilatus - [Praef]ectus Iuda[ea]e - [fecit d]e[dicavit]»].

This is the only archeological evidence of the historical existence of Pontius Pilatus, the prefect of the Roman province of Judaea.

After 6 A.D., Judaea, together with the territories of Samaria and Idumaea, began to be subject to direct Roman rule, its capital being Caesarea Maritima, and the power being exercised by a prefect chosen within the ranks of the equestrian order.

Fig. 43 - Map of first-century Judaea (N. B. Rogers, nineteenth century)

According to historians, between 26 A.D. and 36 A.D. the fifth prefect of Judaea was Pontius Pilate, while, in Rome, Tiberius Caesar was Emperor.

On the origins and family of Pontius Pilatus, ancient sources provide no details, even though according to tradition he may possibly have been born in the Italian region of Abruzzo. Certainly enough, his name and office are explicitly mentioned by many non-Christian historians, providing full historical solidity to a figure who is mainly known, after the Gospels, for his crucial role in the Passion of Jesus Christ.

First-century Roman-Jewish historian Flavius Josephus, in his *The Jewish War* (Book II, folia 90-91 of the precious manuscript Grec 1425 preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France, dating to the eleventh century) portrays a careless, insensitive Pilate, stirring heedlessly up the rage of the Jews subject to his rule by performing acts which were seen as an attack to the local religion and customs:

«Pilate, being sent by Tiberius as procurator to Judaea, introduced into Jerusalem by night and under cover the effigies of Caesar which are called standards. This proceeding, when day broke, aroused immense excitement among the Jews [... as their laws] permit no image to be erected in the city. Hastening after Pilate to Caesarea, the Jews implored him to remove the standards from Jerusalem and to uphold the laws of their ancestors. [...] Pilate refused».

At all appearances, Pilatus also had a taste for vicious, dramatic effects, because what he did in this predicament did not certainly gained to him the approval of the ruled people:

«On the ensuing day Pilate took his seat on his tribunal in the great stadium and summoning the multitude, with the apparent intention of answering them, gave the arranged signal to his armed soldiers to surround the Jews. Finding themselves in a ring of troops, three deep, the Jews were struck dumb at the unexpected sight. Pilate, after threatening to cut them down, if they refused to admit Caesar's images, signalled to the soldiers to draw their swords».

«He, foreseeing the tumult, had interspersed among the crowd a troop of his soldiers, armed but disguised in civilian dress, with orders not to use their swords, but to beat any rioters with cudgels. He now from his tribunal gave the agreed signal. Large numbers of the Jews perished, some from the blows which they received, others trodden to death by their companions in the ensuing flight. Cowed by the fate of the victims, the multitude was reduced to silence».

The portrait of Pontius Pilate provided by Flavius Josephus must not have been so distant from truth, if we consider that a hint to another forgotten massacre is contained in the Gospels themselves, in which we found a short sentence briefly mentioning «the Galilaeans, whose blood Pilate had mingled with their sacrifices» (Luke 13:1), possibly referring to pilgrims carelessly slain by the Romans at the Temple in Jerusalem. And a similar description of the mean Roman prefect can be found in another ancient writer as well: Philo of Alexandria.

Philo was a Jewish author and philosopher who lived in Alexandria, Egypt, in the first century of the Christian era. In his *Legatio ad Gaium* (Chapter XXXVIII) Philo reports a similar episode, possibly the same described by Josephus, which confirms and deepens the outline of Pilate's wicked, cowardly figure:

«Pilate was one of the emperor's lieutenants, having been appointed governor of Judaea. He, not more with the object of doing honour to Tiberius than with that of vexing the multitude, dedicated some gilt shields in the palace of Herod, in the holy city [Jerusalem]».

Again, Philo of Alexandria narrates of a Roman prefect who finds it pleasurable to challenge his subjects and arouse their anger. The most noble representatives of the Jewish people raised a formal grievance against this offence to local laws and customs. However, «he steadfastly refused this petition, for he was a man of a very inflexible disposition, and very merciless as well as very obstinate».

Fig. 46 - The excerpt on Pontius Pilate as it appears in Philo of Alexandria's *Legatio ad Gaium* (Latin edition published in Basel in 1554)

This is the point when the Jews strike a false note, which simply enflames the wrath of Pilate:

«Sure enough Emperor Tiberius is not desirous that any of our laws or customs shall be destroyed. And if you yourself say that he is, show us either some command from him, or some letter, or something of the kind, that we, who have been sent to you as ambassadors, may cease to trouble you, and may address our supplications directly to your master».

There is nothing worse with a powerful man exercising his power in an inappropriate way than to threaten to appeal to his higher-rank supervisor: this menace «exasperated him to the greatest possible degree», as he feared that they might report to Tiberius a comprehensive account of all his robberies, abuses and unlawful behaviour. However, he was just too coward to decide a firm course of action - by the way, just the very same approach he will adopt when confronting with the case of a certain Jesus Christ:

«Therefore, being exceedingly angry, and being at all times a man of most ferocious passions, he was in great perplexity, neither venturing to take down what he had once set up, nor wishing to do any thing which could be

acceptable to his subjects, and at the same time being sufficiently acquainted with the firmness of Tiberius on these points».

But the Jews were much more determined than he was: they resolved to tighten their hold on Pilate, by addressing «a most supplicatory letter to Tiberius».

And results began to flow in:

«When Tiberius had read the letter, what did he say of Pilate, and what threats did he utter against him! [...] How very angry he was [...] Immediately, without putting any thing off till the next day, he wrote a letter, reproaching and reviling him in the most bitter manner for his act of unprecedented audacity, and commanding him immediately to take down the shields». And the shields were taken down.

Fig. 47 - The wrath of Tiberius from Philo of Alexandria's *Legatio ad Gaium* (Latin edition published in Basel in 1554)

So, according to a classical literary tradition, Pontius Pilate, the fifth prefect of Judaea, was not a reliable direct report. As a subordinate official, holding a high-level post as resident ruler and representative of the Emperor of Rome in a small, remote province, he was cause for concerns owing to his careless behaviour, wholly indifferent to the feelings and wishes of his subjects, turbulent as they were. And he sparked turmoil, and unwanted discontent.

This scenario is further confirmed by another excerpt taken from Flavius Josephus. In his *Antiquities of the Jews*, written at the end of the first century, he narrates of a man from Samaria, a region set between Judaea and Galilee, who publicly alleged that he could unearth the ancient, sacred vessels which were buried by Moses himself under the top of a local

mount, called Gerizim. The Samaritans gathered in excitement at a nearby village, the crowd ready to ascend the mount to see the holy vessels.

But Pilate, in full contempt of their expectations and religious beliefs, devised to play one of his usual cruel tricks on them (Book XVIII, Chapter V):

«Pilate prevented their going up, by seizing upon the roads with a great band of horsemen and footmen, who fell upon those that were gotten together in the village; and when it came to an action, some of them they slew, and others of them they put to flight, and took a great many alive, the principal of whom, and also the most potent of those that fled away, Pilate ordered to be slain».

Of course, this brutal way of conducting public order's management in the province was not appreciated by his subjects, and they did not refrain from escalating the matter to Rome's upper political level:

«After that, the Samaritan noblemen sent an embassy to Vitellius, who [...] was now the governor of Syria, and accused Pilate of the murder of those that were killed, out of the fact that they did not go to the village in order to revolt from the Romans, but to escape the violence of Pilate».

Fig. 48 - Pilate and the killing of Samaritans from Flavius Josephus' *Antiquities of the Jews* (Greek-Latin edition published in Geneva in 1611)

The resulting effect of this most legitimate protest was that Pilate was ordered «to go to Rome, to answer before the Emperor to the accusations of the Jews». Therefore, he «made haste to Rome, and this in obedience to the orders of Vitellius, which he dared not contradict». He never returned to Judaea. He had been in charge of Judaea «for ten years», says Josephus, and he had just enough luck to avoid the Emperor's punishment, only because «before he could get to Rome, Tiberius was dead». This occurred in 37 A.D.

Pontius Pilate, coward and cruel as he was, did not prove to be a fit manager of the interests of Rome in a far-off province. He showed a positive tendency to the creation of discontent and commotion amid the populations subject to Roman rule. Philo of Alexandria adds a few effective words to describe the vile and inadequate prefect (*Legatio ad Gaium*, Chapter XXXVIII):

«He feared lest they [the Jews] might in reality go on an embassy to the Emperor, and might reveal some particulars of his government, in respect of his felonies, trade of sentences, and his rapine, and his habit of insulting people, and his massacres, and tortures, and his continual murders of people untried and uncondemned, and his most grievous cruelty».

Fig. 49 - Pontius Pilate's negative traits as portrayed by Philo of Alexandria in his *Legatio ad Gaium* (Latin edition published in Basel in 1554)

According to Josephus, he was also undecided when things went bad, and desirous to retrace his own steps to avoid further troubles, as «he was inclined to change his mind as to what he had done, but that he was not willing to be thought to do so».

That was Pontius Pilate: a mediocre man, whose name History would not celebrate nor remember at all, if not out of the few excerpts written on him by Philo of Alexandria and Flavius Josephus, and a handful of words

recorded on a slab of stone found in a second-rank excavation site in Palestine.

However, History does remember the name of Pontius Pilate.

Because he played a primary, undisputed role in the Passion of Jesus Christ: a fateful event that took place «in the fifteenth year of the reign of Tiberius Caesar, Pontius Pilate being governor of Judaea, and Herod being tetrarch of Galilee» (Luke 3:1).

Fig. 50 - Pontius Pilate as a main character playing a major role in the Passion

Pontius Pilate. A character who, in a most critical predicament whose tale will be told and told again across the centuries to come, will stage any and all of his most despicable qualities, as described by Philo and Josephus: cruelty, straightforward cowardice, a proclivity for hesitation, a nasty sense of humour.

But we also have other fundamental information. In the next article, we will read the words written in a true, first-rank primary source. A source which mentions Pontius Pilate in his role as a Roman Empire's official fully bestowed with plenary powers and authority.

We are going to open the pages of the Gospels, and read about the deeds of Pilate, the fifth Roman prefect of Judaea.

8. The man who let Jesus die

«Pilate then went out unto them, and said, What accusation bring ye against this man?»

Fig. 51 - Jesus Christ is brought before Pontius Pilate (from *Jesus of Nazareth*, a TV miniseries broadcasted in 1977)

This is the opening remark pronounced by Pontius Pilate after his first appearance in the Gospel of John (18:29). Jesus Christ is standing before him, after having been seized by the Jews. They try, in tumult and anger, to induce the Roman ruler of Judaea to sentence him, and sentence him to death.

Pilate begins to question Jesus, but he can «find in him no fault at all» (John 18:38). Under pressure, he makes an attempt at satisfying the populace's crave for blood by scourging Jesus. However, this is not enough for the mob: when he addresses the clamouring Jews by saying «Behold, I bring him forth to you, that ye may know that I find no fault in him» (John 19:4), they call for him to crucify the prisoner.

We can see the above words spoken by Pilate as they appear in the folia 1377 and 1378 of the most antique Codex Vaticanus (Vat. Gr. 1209), preserved at the Vatican Apostolic Library, a precious fourth-century manuscript bearing the oldest extant specimen of the Gospels, in their original Greek version.

Fig. 52 - Pilate finds no fault in Jesus (John 19:4), the Greek text as it appears in the *Codex Vaticanus* (Vat. Gr. 1209), preserved at the Vatican Apostolic Library in Rome, folia 1377 and 1378

Now Pilate finds himself in dire straits. And we know from Flavius Josephus and Philo of Alexandria that when he finds himself in distress the Roman prefect gets less vicious and increasingly hesitant.

He tries to discard the case by telling the leaders of the Jews «take ye him, and crucify him: for I find no fault in him» (John 19:6), stating for the third time that he thinks that Jesus is guilty of nothing.

But the reaction is vehement, and the Roman prefect «was the more afraid» (John 19:8).

Fig. 53 - Pilate's fear (John 19:8), with the Greek word for 'scared' highlighted (*Codex Vaticanus* - Vat. Gr. 1209, Vatican Apostolic Library, folium 1378)

He is scared, and we see this fundamental Greek word enlarged in the figure. He fears grave consequences for his rule and his own personal safety if he does not give in to the requests made by the Jews and their leaders. In this predicament, he utters the most famous questions «What is truth?» (John 18:38); yet this is no philosopher's enquiry, but just a makeshift attempt to gain additional time, thinking and rethinking in his mind how to escape this dangerous predicament.

Fig. 54 - «What is the truth?» (John 18:38) from the *Codex Vaticanus* (Vat. Gr. 1209, Vatican Apostolic Library, folium 1377)

This is the very moment in which, according to an antique tradition, Pontius Pilate begins to be loaded with his own grave, fateful, unforgivable guilt: he gives up to the Jews, and consents to proceeding with the execution of Jesus Christ, the Son of God.

He himself tells Jesus the words which will mark his own personal doom for the centuries to come: «knowest thou not that I have power to crucify thee, and have power to release thee?» (John 19:10). But, as we will see

later, he had no such powers: a power that only belongs to God, according to the early-Christian exegetic tradition.

Fig. 55 - Pilate's power to release or sentence to death (John 19:10) with the word for 'power', 'authority' highlighted twice, from the *Codex Vaticanus* (Vat. Gr. 1209, Vatican Apostolic Library, folium 1378)

He might command to release Jesus. He had the powers to acquit him of any accusations. But he didn't. He decided to fulfil the will of the roaring Jews. Out of fear. For, they said, «if thou let this man go, thou art not the friend of Caesar: whosoever maketh himself a king speaketh against Caesar» (John 19:12).

«And Pilate gave sentence that it should be as they required» (Luke 23:24).
«Then Pilate delivered him therefore unto them to be crucified. And they took Jesus, and led him away» (John 19:16).

This indelible stain will mark Pilate's memory forever. And his figure, standing out from history, will always be remembered with the few powerful traits depicted in the Gospel of Matthew:

«When Pilate saw that he could prevail nothing, but that rather a tumult was made, he took water, and washed his hands before the multitude, saying, I am innocent of the blood of this just person: see ye to it» (Matthew 27:24).

Thus, in his cowardice, «Pilate, willing to content the people, [...] delivered Jesus [...] to be crucified» (Mark 15:15).

But when pressure on him lessens, Pontius Pilate regains his distinguishing traits and habits, which we already know from Philo and Josephus. So he does not miss the opportunity to show his nasty, sadistic penchant: «And Pilate wrote a title, and put it on the cross. And the writing was, 'Jesus of Nazareth the King of the Jews'» (John 19:19).

This is a reference to the most famous 'Titulus Crucis' ('Title of the Cross'), the written piece of wood that was placed on the top of the Cross by the Roman soldiers, by the order of Pilate himself. The wood which is traditionally believed to be possibly this original artifact is currently preserved at the Church of Santa Croce in Gerusalemme in Rome.

Fig. 56 - The 'Titulus Crucis' preserved at the Basilica of Santa Croce in Gerusalemme, Rome

According to the Gospel of John, at this point Pilate is still capable of a last, useless stand inspired to firmness and uprightness: when the Jews ask him to take that inappropriate, nonsensical writing off, he drily replies to them «What I have written I have written» (John 19:22). This will be the only sign of dauntlessness shown by Pilate in the whole affair.

Here ends our overview of the most ancient literary tradition concerning the figure of the fifth Roman prefect of Judaea.

Fig. 57 - «What I have written I have written» (John 19:22) from the *Codex Vaticanus* (Vat. Gr. 1209, Vatican Apostolic Library, folium 1378)

However, a question still remains: what has it all got to do with a small lake sitting within the glacial cirque of a mountainous chain in Italy? What has this story to do with the Sibillini Mountain Range?

To find the link, we still have to illustrate the heritage left by Pontius Pilate to the subsequent ages. A heritage of contempt and repugnance.

And curse.

Michele Sanvico

END OF PART 1

**Please refer to Part 2 and Part 3
for the continuation of this research paper**